

Condensation of Pimelyl Chloride and Suberyl Chloride with Phenols and Phenolic Ethers

D. Chakravarti and (Mrs.) Anjali Chakravarti

Pimelyl chloride and suberyl chloride have been condensed with phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols and their methyl ethers in presence of aluminium chloride forming 1, 7-diketones and 6-keto acids and 1, 8-diketones and 7-keto-acids respectively.

In earlier papers Chakravarti and coworkers^{1,2} have shown that glutaryl chloride and adipyl chloride when condensed with free phenols in presence of aluminium chloride in the presence of a solvent e.g., nitrobenzene, yield mainly *p*-hydroxy keto-acids in good yield, along with the diketones. When the *p*-position of the phenol is substituted glutaryl chloride and adipyl chloride yield esters (A) and not a trace of diketone or keto acid.

In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of pimelyl and suberyl chloride with phenols and phenolic ethers. In the case of pimelyl chloride and suberyl chloride, however, *p*-substituted phenols yield *o*-hydroxy diketones and keto acids. The condensations of *p*-chlorophenol with pimelyl and suberyl chloride yield only keto acids and the diketones are not obtained.

Phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols and their methyl ethers condense with pimelyl and suberyl chloride forming 1,7 and 1,8-diketones (I) and 6- and 7-keto acids (II) respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of pimelyl chloride, $\text{Cl-CO-(CH}_2)_5\text{-COCl}$ and suberyl chloride, $\text{ClCO-(CH}_2)_6\text{-COCl}$.

Pimelyl chloride (b.p. 140–45°/5 mm) and suberyl chloride (b.p. 140–50°/5 mm) are obtained from *dry* pimelic acid and *dry* suberic acid by treatment with thionyl chloride in the usual manner.

1, 7-bis(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) heptane-1, 7-dione (I, $R_2 = \text{OH}$; $R = R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$; $n = 5$).

1. *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 607.

2. *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 33.

A solution of freshly distilled phenol (2 g.) in nitrobenzene (30 ml.) was taken in a 250 ml. 3-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a CaCl_2 guard tube. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (4 g.) was added to the solution maintained at $0^\circ\text{--}5^\circ$. A solution of pimelyl chloride (1.9 g.) in nitrobenzene (10 ml.) was added through the dropping funnel over a period of one hr. The stirring was continued for a further period of 4 hrs at room temperature. The product was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and distilled with steam to remove excess of nitrobenzene. The crude product solidified on cooling for about 12 hrs. It was insoluble in NaHCO_3 solution. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 55° (Found : C, 73.00; H, 6.39. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$: C, 73.08; H, 6.4%). It does not give any coloration with ferric chloride. The 2 : 4-D.N.P. crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 195° (Found : N, 16.82, Calc. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_8$: N, 16.67%).

The structure of the above diketone is confirmed thus : (a) On methylation of the diketone with dimethyl sulphate 1,7-bis (*p*-methoxy-phenyl) heptane 1,7-dione, is obtained which is identical with the diketone obtained from anisole and pimelyl chloride. *p*-Anisic acid is obtained by oxidation of 1,7-bis (*p*-methoxy phenyl) heptane 1,7-dione with alkaline potassium permanganate.

The compounds prepared with other phenols and phenolic ethers prepared in the same way are described in Table I. The compounds prepared with suberyl chloride are described in Table II.

TABLE I

Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic ethers with Pimelyl chloride

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found	Reqd.	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
anisole	1,7-bis [<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl] heptane-1,7-dione, prismatic rods (alcohol), m.p. 100°.	[R ₂ = OMe R = R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H <i>n</i> = 5] C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	C, 74.11 H, 6.96	C, 74.12 H, 7.06	m.p. 150° (Yellow, needles) (Found : N, 16.3. C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 16%).	On oxidation gives <i>p</i> -anisic acid; m.p. 184°.
<i>O</i> -cresol	1,7-bis [3-methyl-4-hydroxy phenyl] heptane-1,7-dione crystallised from alcohol. m.p. 110°.	[R ₂ = OH R = R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H <i>n</i> = 5] C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	C, 74.01 H, 7.00	C, 74.12 H, 7.06	m.p. 203°. Yellow needles (Found : requires N, 16%).	No colouration with ferric chloride.. Methylation gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>O</i> -cresol methyl ether with Pimelyl chloride.
<i>O</i> -cresol methyl ether.	(a) 1,7-bis [3-methyl-4-methoxy phenyl] heptane 1,7-dione. Crystallised from alcohol m.p. 120°.	[R ₂ = OMe, R ₃ = CH ₃ R = R ₁ = R ₄ = H <i>n</i> = 5] C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₄	C, 74.99 H, 7.56	C, 75.00 H, 7.61	m.p. 170° (Found : N, 15.66 : C ₃₅ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 15.38%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ . Oxidation by alkaline KMnO ₄ gives 4-methoxy-isophthalic acid, m.p. 273° (mixed m.p.)
	(b) 5-(3-methyl-4-methoxy benzoyl) hexoic acid, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 165°.	[R ₂ = OMe, R ₃ = CH ₃ R ₁ = R = R ₄ = H <i>n</i> = 5] C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄	C, 68.10 H, 7.49	C, 68.18 H, 7.58	m.p. 170° (Found : N, 11.61. C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 12.61%).	
<i>m</i> -cresol	(a) 1,7-bis [<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl phenyl] heptane 1,7-dione, prismatic rods from alcohol, m.p. 100°.	[R ₂ = OH, R ₄ = CH ₃ R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H <i>n</i> = 5]. C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	C, 74.00 H, 6.84	C, 74.12 H, 7.06	m.p. 155° (Found : N, 16.09. C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 16%).	On methylation gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether and pimelyl chloride. On oxidation it gives 4-methoxy phthalic acid m.p. 169°.

TABLE I—(Continued)
Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic ethers with Pimelyl chloride

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found	Reqd.	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.F.)	Remarks
	(b) 5-(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -toluyl benzoyl)-hexoic acid crystallised from hot water, m.p. 105°.	[R ₂ = OH, R ₄ = CH ₃ R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H n = 5] C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ .	C, 67.12 H, 7.10	C, 67.20 H, 7.20	m.p. 185° (Found : C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ requires N, 13.02%); m.p. 13.30; C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ requires N, 13.02%.	On methylation gave 5-(<i>p</i> -methoxy- <i>o</i> -toluyl benzoyl) hexoic acid, m.p. 90°, which on oxidation gives 4-methoxy phthalic acid, m.p. 168° (mixed m.p.).
<i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether.	1,7 bis [<i>p</i> -methoxy- <i>o</i> -toluyl phenyl] heptane, 1,7 dione, crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 115°.	(I) [R ₂ = OMe, R ₄ = CH ₃ R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H n = 5]. C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄ .	C, 74.89 H, 7.60	C, 75.00 H, 7.61	m.p. 200° (Found : N, 15.49; C ₃₅ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 15.38%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ .
<i>p</i> -chloro-phenol	5-(<i>o</i> -hydroxy-5-chloro benzoyl) hexoic acid crystallised from dilute alcohol m.p. 119°	(II) [R = R ₂ = R ₃ = H, R ₁ = Cl, R ₄ = OH n = 5]. C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₄ Cl.	C, 57.86 H, 5.57	C, 57.67 H, 5.54	m.p. 178° (Found : N, 12.20. C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₄ Cl requires N, 12.65%).	
<i>p</i> -chloro- <i>m</i> -cresol.	(a) 5-(2-hydroxy-5-chloro 6-methyl benzoyl) hexoic acid or 5-(2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4-methyl benzoyl) hexoic acid. Crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol m.p. 148°.	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl.	C, 59.20 H, 5.99	C, 59.05 H, 5.97	m.p. 129° (Found : N, 12.02; C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₄ Cl requires N, 12.05%).	
	(b) 1,7-bis (2-hydroxy-5-chloro 6-methyl phenyl)heptane 1,7 dione.	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ Cl ₂	C, 61.81 H, 5.43	C, 61.61 H, 5.38	m.p. 208° (Found N, 14.50. C ₃₃ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₁₀ Cl ₂ requires N, 14.56%).	
	or 1,7 bis (2-hydroxy-5-chloro 4-methyl phenyl) heptane 1 : 7 dione. Prismatic rods from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 120°.					
<i>p</i> -cresol	1,7 bis (<i>o</i> -hydroxy- <i>p</i> -toluyl phenyl) heptane 1,7 dione, crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 140°.	[R = R ₂ = R ₃ = H R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₄ = OH n = 5]. C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄ .	C, 74.10 H, 6.84	C, 74.12 H, 7.06	m.p. 190° (Found : N, 16.09. C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 16%).	

TABLE II
Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic Ethers with Suberyl Chloride

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found	Reqd.	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.P.)	Remarks
Phenol	(a) 6-(<i>p</i> -hydroxy benzoyl) heptonic acid. Colourless needles from hot water, m.p. 129°.	(I) $R_1=R_2=OH, n=6$ $R_3=R_4=H$ $C_{14}H_{16}O_4$	C, 67.0 H, 7.00	C, 67.20 H, 7.20	m.p. 250°, (Found: N, 13.30; $C_{20}H_{22}N_4O_7$ requires N, 13.02%).	No coloration with $FeCl_3$. On methylation gave a product identical with the keto acid obtained from anisole and suberyl chloride. On oxidation it gives <i>p</i> -anisic acid m.p. 184° (mixed m.p.).
	(b) 1,8 bis (<i>p</i> -Hydroxy phenyl) octane 1,8 dione. Crystallised from dilute alcohol m.p. 200°.	(I) $R_1=R_2=OH, n=6$ $R_3=R_4=H$ $C_{20}H_{22}O_4$	C, 73.93 H, 7.13	C, 73.62 H, 6.75	m.p. 150. (Found: N, 16.40, $C_{32}H_{34}O_{10}N_6$ requires N, 16.33%).	On methylation gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from anisole and suberyl chloride. On oxidation it gives <i>p</i> -anisic acid, m.p. 184° (mixed m.p.).
Anisole	(a) 6-(<i>p</i> -methoxy benzoyl) heptonic acid. Crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 114°.	(I) $R_1=R_2=OCH_3, n=6$ $R_3=R_4=H$ $C_{15}H_{20}O_4$	C, 68.0 H, 7.23	C, 68.18 H, 7.58	m.p. 180°, (Found: N, 12.90, $C_{21}H_{22}N_4O_7$ requires N, 12.61%).	No coloration with $FeCl_3$.
	(b) 1,8 bis (<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl) octane 1,8 dione. Prismatic rods from alcohol, m.p. 133°.	(I) $R_1=R_2=OCH_3, n=6$ $R_3=R_4=H$ $C_{22}H_{26}O_4$	C, 74.49 H, 7.12	C, 74.58 H, 7.34	m.p. 200°, (Found: N, 15.40, $C_{34}H_{36}O_{10}N_6$ requires N, 15.69%).	No coloration with $FeCl_3$.
o-Cresol	(a) 6-(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>m</i> -toluyl benzoyl) heptonic acid needles from dilute ethyl alcohol, m.p. 102°.	(I) $R_1=R_2=OH, R_3=CH_3, n=6$ $C_{15}H_{20}O_4$	C, 68.00 H, 7.49	C, 68.18 H, 7.58	m.p. 140°, (Found: N, 12.46, $C_{21}H_{22}N_4O_7$ requires N, 12.61%).	Methylation gave product 6-(<i>p</i> -methoxy- <i>m</i> -toluyl benzoyl), heptonic acid, m.p. 150° on oxidation gives 4-methoxy isophthalic acid, m.p. 274° (mixed m.p.).
	(b) 1,8 bis (3-methyl-4-hydroxy phenyl) octane 1,8 dione. Prismatic rods from ethyl alcohol m.p. 190°.	(I) $R_1=R_2=OH, R_3=CH_3, n=6$ $C_{22}H_{26}O_4$	C, 74.50 H, 7.29	C, 74.58 H, 7.34	m.p. 250°, (Found: N, 15.50, $C_{34}H_{36}N_6O_{10}$ requires N, 15.69%).	Methylation of the diketone gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether and suberyl chloride. On oxidation it gives 4-methoxy isophthalic acid, m.p. 274° (mixed m.p.).

TABLE II—(Continued)
Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic Ethers with Suberyl Chloride.

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found	Reqd.	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
<i>o</i> -Cresol ether	1,8 bis (3-methyl-4-methoxy phenyl) octane 1,8 dione. Prismatic rods from alcohol m.p. 131°.	(I) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = H$, $R_5 = OMe$, $R_6 = CH_3$, $n = 6$, $C_{24}H_{30}O_4$.	C, 75.18 H, 7.66	C, 75.39 H, 7.85	m.p. 200° (Found : N, 15.20 requires N, 15.09%).	No colouration with $FeCl_3$.
<i>m</i> -cresol	(a) 6-(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl benzoyl) heptotic acid. Crystallised from hot water m.p. 95°.	(II) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $R_4 = OH$, $R_5 = CH_3$, $n = 6$, $C_{13}H_{20}O_4$.	C, 68.10 H, 7.30	C, 68.18 H, 7.58	m.p. 180° (Found : N, 12.37. $C_{31}H_{34}N_4O_7$ requires N, 12.61%).	On methylation it gave a product identical with the keto acid obtained from <i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether and suberyl chloride, which on oxidation gives 4-methoxy phthalic acid, m.p. 170° (mixed m.p.).
	(b) 1,8 bis (<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl phenyl) octane 1,8 dione. Prismatic rods from ethyl alcohol m.p. 110°.	(I) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $R_4 = OH$, $R_5 = CH_3$, $n = 6$, $C_{22}H_{26}O_4$.	C, 74.50 H, 7.29	C, 74.58 H, 7.34	m.p. 207° (Found : N, 15.50, $C_{34}H_{38}N_4O_{10}$ requires N, 15.69%).	Methylation of the di-ketone gave 1,8 bis (2-methyl-4-methoxy phenyl) octane 1,8 dione which on oxidation gives 4-methoxy phthalic acid m.p. 168° (mixed m.p.).
<i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether.	6-(<i>p</i> -methoxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl benzoyl) heptotic acid. Crystallised from hot water as needles, m.p. 101°.	(II) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $R_4 = OMe$, $R_5 = CH_3$, $n = 6$, $C_{16}H_{22}O_4$.	C, 68.90 H, 7.72	C, 69.06 H, 7.91	m.p. 120° (Found : N, 12.80. $C_{22}H_{26}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.23%).	
<i>p</i> -chloro phenol	6-(<i>o</i> -hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl) heptotic acid. Crystallised from dilute alcohol m.p. 132°.	(II) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $R_4 = Cl$, $R_5 = OH$, $n = 6$, $C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$.	C, 59.00 H, 5.72	C, 59.05 H, 5.98	m.p. 190° (Found : N, 12.00. $C_{20}H_{21}O_7N_4Cl$ requires N, 12.06%).	
<i>p</i> -cresol	(a) 6-(<i>O</i> -hydroxy-5-tolyl benzoyl) heptotic acid. Prismatic rods from alcohol, m.p. 122°.	(II) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $R_4 = CH_3$, $R_5 = OH$, $n = 6$, $C_{15}H_{20}O_4$.	C, 68.00 H, 7.49	C, 68.18 H, 7.58	m.p. 170° (Found : N, 12.8, $C_{21}H_{24}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.6%).	
	(b) 1,8 bis (<i>O</i> -hydroxy-5-tolyl phenyl) Octane 1,8-dione. Crystallised from alcohol m.p. 110°.	(I) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $R_4 = CH_3$, $R_5 = OH$, $n = 6$, $C_{22}H_{26}O_4$.	C, 74.32 H, 7.30	C, 74.58 H, 7.34	m.p. 200° (Found : N, 15.80. $C_{34}H_{34}O_{10}N_8$ requires N, 15.69%).	

TABLE II—(Continued)
Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic Ethers with Suberyl Chloride.

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found	Reqd.	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
2-Chloro-5-hydroxy toluene	(a) 6-(2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4-methyl benzoyl) heptonic acid.	$C_{15}H_{19}O_4Cl$	C, 60.61 H, 6.40	C, 60.30 H, 6.37	m.p. 220°, (Found : N, 11.82, $C_{21}H_{23}N_3O_7Cl$ requires N, 11.70%).	
	<i>Or</i> 6-(2-hydroxy-5-chloro-6-methyl benzoyl) heptonic acid Crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol m.p. 135°.					
	(b) 1,8 bis (2-hydroxy-5-chloro-6-methyl phenyl) octane 1,8 dione.	$C_{22}H_{24}O_4Cl_2$	C, 62.30 H, 5.49	C, 62.41 H, 5.67	m.p. 125°, (Found : N, 14.39, $C_{33}H_{32}N_8O_{10}Cl_2$ requires N, 14.30%).	Colouration with $FeCl_3$.
	<i>Or</i> 1,8 bis (2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro phenyl)-octane 1,8 dione. Prismatic rods from alcohol, m.p. 115°.					

Chemical Laboratory,
 University College of Science,
 Calcutta-9.

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